

What happens when you miss the right lens

When you use a microscope, you typically have a choice of a few lenses to see the object of interest well. However, occasionally your object happens to be of such size and shape that none of the provided lenses works well enough. It falls 'between the lenses' (<https://philpapers.org/rec/MARWHW-3>).

This happens in science far more often than might be expected. The existing theories (providing the 'why') for the observed laws (providing the 'what') have typically fairly well delineated boundary limits of applicability. Often there are quite wide gaps between them - the cognitive lenses are missing.

Let me give an example from my own fields: chemistry and materials sciences - both are about matter and its transformations. Nowadays we have tools not only to treat the subject at the descriptive, 'substance' level but we can look into it and test concepts about its internal structures and resulting behaviour. If we start at the microscopic, atomic level we are in the realm of quantum chemistry and the famous Schrödinger equation. The problem is that at its most rigorous level (the *ab-initio* models) structures of molecules having only tens to thousands of atoms (depending on the method and computational power available) can be successfully calculated. There are quite good semi-empirical and empirical methods that can push this limit to large protein-sized objects, but at the cost of decreasing precision. However, not for larger systems.

Approaching from the macroscopic end - say, a car or a bridge - one of the most popular models, based on Continuum Mechanics, is the Finite Element Method (FEM). It is still the undisputed gold standard for structural mechanics and solid stress analysis. It cuts the object into small pieces (finite elements) and calculates the physical properties of the whole, summing up the behaviour of these Lego blocks. However, here is the catch. Each element is treated as homogeneous material - its internal molecular architecture is neglected. The method is very successful, but its accuracy depends strongly on assumptions, boundary conditions, and computational approaches.

Most importantly, we are currently unable to bridge the atomic and macroscopic scales. This is not unique to materials science and lots of interesting and practically important questions lie right there. For example, another area suffering from the absence of the right lens is the human brain. We understand many of the underlying neuronal mechanisms, but we still lack the bridge between these bio-physical processes and subjective conscious experience. And, perhaps, the most famous example is the unresolved tension between Quantum Mechanics and General Relativity. Each theory works remarkably well within its own domain, yet no accepted framework can successfully bridge them.

In each of these cases it is the gap between the well-established scientific and engineering domains which is the problem. These lenses are still missing. They deserve to be treated as major scientific challenges, not as nuisances. This might help reshaping our epistemic capability cones (<https://philpapers.org/rec/MARWAE-9>), possibly triggering the paradigm shifts we need.

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